

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE TRANSVERSE COEFFICIENT OF HYGROEXPANSION OF WOOD FIBRES IN COMPOSITE PREFORMS

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SUMMARY: Wood and other cellulosic fibres have many advantages as reinforcement in composite materials compared with conventional manmade fibres. The low price, recyclability and high specific mechanical properties are some of the benefits. A disadvantage is the high degree of hygroexpansion of wood fibres. An experimental procedure has been developed to determine the effective hygroexpansion coefficient of wood fibres from the curvature change of fibre mats at different relative humidity. Fibre mats, which are preforms for composites, generally have a gradient in fibre orientation distribution through the thickness. This gradient in fibre orientation has been characterized through the fibre mat by an image analysis method. A micromechanical laminate model was used to relate the fibre stiffness parameters and hygroexpansion coefficient of each layer based on the fibre orientation distribution. The measured curvature was used as input in a laminate model where the thickness change was taken into consideration. The effective transverse hygroexpansion coefficient was then determined from a relatively simple macroscopic model. For unbleached kraft pulp fibres, the value became 0.11 % strain / % change in moisture content, which is not far from values arduously determined from single wood fibres. The presented method could be used to rank different fibre qualities according to their potential as reinforcement in composites with improved hygroscopic dimensional stability.

KEYWORDS: wood fibre, composite, hygroexpansion, curl, dimensional stability

INTRODUCTION

The pulp and paper industry produces very large quantities of wood fibres at low cost per weight. These fibres are suited for paper and board applications. The mechanical properties of these materials are important although they are not used as structural materials. Because of the fibres are separated and have a relatively high aspect ratio they can be used as reinforcement in composite materials for load bearing applications. The volume of wood fibres processed in pulp and paper mills is enormous and a small fraction of these fibres could be tapped and used as raw material for composites at a low cost. A large share of wood composites are made by extruding parts from wood flour with a thermoplastic that give a fairly weak bond to the wood filler. If wood fibres similar to those in paper were used in composite, better mechanical properties are expected, since these fibres are elongated. Stress can therefore easily be transferred to and from the fibres, and they do not merely give rise to stress concentrations. In paper, the fibres are relatively flexible to assure a large bond area between fibres. Stress is transferred between fibres through the fibre-fibre bonds. In a composite, the load is transferred through the polymer matrix between the fibres. Stiffer and less flexible fibres would therefore be more useful to assure a stiffer composite. Wood fibres that are suitable in paper materials may not be the best fibres to use as composite reinforcement. The first question to ask is what are the desired properties of wood fibres to be used as a constituent in composites. High aspect ratio, high stiffness and low moisture expansion are three required properties.

Wood fibres have many advantageous properties. They come from a renewable resource and are natural, inexpensive, recyclable, degradable and quite stiff and strong. One disadvantage with cellulose-based fibres compared with conventional fibres for composites, e.g. carbon and aramid fibres, is that they are sensitive to moisture. Because of the abundance of hydroxyl end-groups in the

cellulose of the cell-wall of the wood fibres, the fibres will swell in the presence of water. Mechanical properties, such as stiffness and strength, are known to be affected by the ingress of moisture in lignocellulosic-fibre reinforced plastics [1]. These materials also tend to swell considerably at water uptake (see e.g. Refs. 2 and 3), both in the plane of the composite panel and in the thickness direction. Composite panels used in structural applications are usually subject to relatively tight tolerances for the dimensional stability. If the wood-fibre composite panels swell, as the inevitably do, structural members may buckle, snap out of their position or even lead to failure. Panels in cars, furniture, laminate floors etc. could deflect and result in undue deformation because of seasonal changes in humidity. This is an effect that may be noticed in laminated floors. The fibres tend to swell more than the polymer matrix, and the dimensional stability of the composite is therefore sensitive to the fibre content and its spatial distribution in the composite, as well as the orientation distribution of the fibres.

In the present investigation, the out-of-plane buckling of wood-fibre mats has been studied experimentally and modelled by laminate mechanics. A method to determine the effective hygroexpansion coefficient of the fibres given the orientation distribution of the fibres is outlined. The same methodology would also apply to the composite, although the effects are stronger in the preform fibre mat. If the propensity to moisture expansion of different types of wood fibres can be assessed for the fibre mats before the composites are manufacture, the best fibres with respect to dimensional stability could be determined at an earlier stage, as a step to assure a more rational quality control. The first experimental step is to measure the variation in fibre-orientation distribution through the thickness of the fibre mat. In most sheet formation procedures, the fibre mat becomes unsymmetric which results in an elastic coupling between extension and bending. More importantly, the moisture expansion will result in curl of the fibre mat and also in the final composite. If the curl is characterized for different moisture contents, laminate mechanics and composite micromechanics models can be used to estimate the hygroexpansion coefficient of the fibres. The present approach is essentially based on the work of Carlsson [4]. The micromechanical model to link to laminate behaviour to the fibrous microstructure relies in part to the work of Schulgasser [5] on hygroexpansion and of Schulgasser and Page [6] on elasticity.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Materials and preform manufacture: Unbleached softwood kraft fibres were used. Hand chipped and screened *Picea Abies* were cooked and processed according conventional procedures to a kappa number of 46. Oriented fibre mats or sheets were prepared from the pulp sample using a dynamic sheet former Formette Dynamique [7], which forms the sheet on a wire on the inside of a rotating drum. The fibre deposition takes place by centrifugation through a water layer. The centrifugal forces make the fibres settle and form an evenly distributed sheet on the wire, and also assist in the dewatering process when the forming is completed. The dynamic sheet formation allows a large span of different angular speeds of the drum and fibre suspension flows at the inlet, which means that it is possible to control the jet-to-wire speed difference in order to produce sheets with desired anisotropy. Adjusting the jet-to-wire speed difference makes it possible to control the alignment of the fibres in the direction of rotation, and thus makes the dynamic sheet former suitable for manufacturing oriented reinforcing fibre mats for composite applications.

Never dried fibres were separated in water and the fibre suspension was applied on the rotating wire. The drum speed of 1450 rpm and a pump pressure of 2.8 bars were used, i.e. the fibre mat was formed in drag conditions with an approximate jet to wire speed difference of -2.5 m/s. The contraction ratio of the nozzle was approximately 4.5. The fibre mat was pressed with a double felt roll with one nip at one bar. Restrained drying was then preformed at 23°C and 50% relative humidity for more than 24 hours. The fibres of the obtained fibre mat were thus oriented predominantly in the machine direction (MD). The grammage was 185 g/m².

Test methods: The test procedures can be divided into two parts: (i) splitting of the fibre mat into layers using adhesive tape and scanning of the layers into images used for analysis and (ii) determining the curvature and thickness of the fibre mat at different relative humidity.

To experimentally determine the in-plane orientation of the fibres through the thickness of the fibre mat, the original fibre mat was split into a large number of individual layers. This was done

by a tape-splitting technique. Similar layer orientation measurements have also been reported in [8] and [9]. First a strip of the size 50 mm in MD and 200 mm in the cross direction (CD) was cut from the fibre mat. The strip was then split in two parts using adhesive tape (transparent polyester based film). These layers were subsequently split in two new layers, which was repeated until 77 layers of appropriate grammage were obtained. The principles for the splitting procedure are schematically shown in Fig. 1. The individual layers should contain a sufficient amount of fibres for image analysis of the fibre orientation distribution. Since the fibres and fibre bundles are distinguished from the background, too many overlapping fibres would mask the direction of the fibres. Too few fibres would not give sufficient data to accurately estimate the distribution parameters of the fibre orientation.

Fig. 1 The principles of the splitting procedure. Adhesive tape was used to pull layers of fibres off the surfaces of other layers.

When the splitting procedure was finished each layer was sorted and marked with a number, starting from 1 at the topside (Fig. 1). Each layer was then placed against a dark background (black paper) and was scanned using a desktop scanner with an optical resolution of 600 x 600 dpi in reflectance mode.

The software package FIBOR (STFI Fibre Orientation Software) was used to characterize the fibre orientation distribution. The numerical value of each pixel in the digital images of each fibre layer is a measure of the greyscale level at that location in the image, and ranges from 0 (black) to 255 (white). The fibres are distinguished as light entities against the dark background in the image of the thin layer surfaces. The software utilises gradient analysis by edge detection to determine the fibre orientation distribution. Gradient analysis uses the Sobel operator to discover fibre edges, which represent abrupt discontinuities of image brightness. The result can be classified in histograms with relative number of fibres in each angle interval with respect to MD. One possible disadvantage with the method outlined above is the sensibility of the Sobel operator to noise. Nevertheless other studies that characterize the fibre orientation distribution with digital image processing techniques that use the gradient method have been proven successful [10]. The software was calibrated with simulated fibre orientation distributions. The grammage of each layer was estimated from the relative fibre content in each image. The relative grammage of each layer was determined by calculating the fraction of the fibres in each image of the layer using image analysis. The images were first thresholded to separate out the background regions.

The curvature of the fibre mat at different relative humidity was also characterized by an image analysis technique. A total amount of 14 rectangular shaped strips were cut from the fibre mats with dimensions of 140 mm x 8 mm (CD x MD). Twelve specimens were used for curvature measurements and two for thickness measurement. The strips were centrally supported in a standing position along their long edges by pins attached to small piece of rubber (see Fig. 2). The supports held the specimen in an upright position and the large width-to-thickness ratio precludes any significant influence from gravity in the free deflecting parts of the strips. Friction from the support and gravitational forces could then be neglected. A millimetre paper was placed underneath as a scale in the images.

Fig. 2 Experimental set-up for the curvature measurements at ambient temperature of 22 °C and 50% RH inside the sealing bag.

The fibre mat strips were placed inside a transparent plastic bag that was sealed and connected to a moisture generator and a vacuum pump. In that way the air flow and the relative humidity inside the plastic bag could be controlled. All tests were performed under equilibrium conditions of temperature and humidity. As it is preferable to monitor the properties of each specimen as a function of moisture content rather than relative humidity (see e.g. Ref. 11), an equilibrium sorption isotherm at 30 °C in adsorption for the fibre mat was performed with an automated dynamic vapour sorption equipment (DVS, Surface Measurement Systems Ltd). The fibre mat strips were conditioned in the transparent plastic bag at ambient temperature of 22 °C and relative humidity (RH) of 0% RH (dry air flow) respective 50% RH (air flow at 30 °C and 31.14% RH) for at least 24 hours to achieve equilibrium. Digital images were taken of the curled strips from above (zenith) to measure the curvature.

The thickness of the fibre mat at 0% RH and 50% RH was measured with two surface profilometers on the opposite sides of a nip through which the specimens were pulled. The apparatus is carefully calibrated with a reference thickness, from which a deviation is measured [12].

LAMINATE MECHANICS

The layered fibre mat is considered as a laminate where an orthotropic constitutive relation describes the in-plane properties of each constituent layer or ply. Hygroscopic strains in the laminate result from changes in the moisture content of the laminate. These strains are assumed to depend linearly on the moisture content over the humidity range under investigation. This proportionality is given by coefficients of moisture expansion. If the laminate is completely free to expand, bend and twist when subjected to a change in moisture content ΔC , from a given moisture content C_1 to another C_2 , the relationship between the changes in fictitious hygroscopic forces and moments $\{\Delta N^H\}$ and $\{\Delta M^H\}$ that produce the changes in the midplane strains $\{\Delta \varepsilon^0\}$ and plate curvatures $\{\Delta \kappa\}$ can be expressed as

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \Delta N^H \\ \Delta M^H \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{A} & \bar{B} \\ \bar{B} & \bar{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta \varepsilon^0 \\ \Delta \kappa \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The $[\bar{A}]$, $[\bar{B}]$ and $[\bar{D}]$ matrices are defined as the effective extensional stiffness matrix $[A]$, extension-bending coupling stiffness matrix $[B]$ and bending stiffness matrix $[D]$, respectively, taking the gradual change in thickness into account. The thickness is assumed to change t_1 to t_2 linearly with respect to the moisture content. If the matrices $[A]$, $[B]$ and $[D]$ refer to the final thickness t_2 , then the modified stiffness matrices of the laminate are given by

$$[\bar{A}] = \frac{\langle t \rangle}{t_2} [A] \quad [\bar{B}] = \frac{\langle t^2 \rangle}{t_2^2} [B] \quad [\bar{D}] = \frac{\langle t^3 \rangle}{t_2^3} [D] \quad (2)$$

where $\langle t \rangle$, $\langle t^2 \rangle$ and $\langle t^3 \rangle$ are the first, second and third order moments about the origin of the thickness values. The hygroscopic forces and moments can be evaluated from the hygroscopic strains induced in the laminate by a uniform change in moisture content ΔC in the laminate. Integrating the ply stresses induced by the constraints placed on its deformation by adjacent plies and accounting for an increase in thickness of the laminate, the hygroscopic force and moment vectors can be calculated as

$$\{\Delta N^H\} = \Delta C \langle t \rangle \sum_{i=1}^n [\bar{Q}]_i \{\bar{\beta}\}_i (z_i - z_{i-1}) \quad (3)$$

$$\{\Delta M^H\} = \frac{\Delta C \langle t^2 \rangle}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n [\bar{Q}]_i \{\bar{\beta}\}_i (z_i^2 - z_{i-1}^2) \quad (4)$$

where $[\bar{Q}]_i$ is the effective global stiffness matrix of layer i , $\{\bar{\beta}\}_i$ is a vector with the apparent coefficients of moisture expansion for layer i and z_i are ply coordinates normalised with the thickness of the laminate.

As in the work of Carlsson [4], Eq. (1) can be rewritten into an explicit expression of the curvatures in a fibre mat consisting of an arbitrary number of plies with a given orientation of the constituent plies,

$$\{\Delta \kappa\} = [B^*]^{-1} (\{\Delta M^H\} - [A^*] \{\Delta N^H\}) \quad (5)$$

where

$$[A^*] = [\bar{B}][\bar{A}]^{-1} \quad (6)$$

$$[B^*] = -[\bar{B}][\bar{A}]^{-1}[\bar{B}] + [\bar{D}] \quad (7)$$

The elastic properties of wood fibres are highly anisotropic, and the stiffness parameters depend primarily on the fibril angle in the cell wall. The helical structure of the fibre implies that axial deformation is coupled with torsion. Taking this coupling into account would require a very detailed analysis which is not necessary in the present investigation. Instead, the fibres are assumed to be transversely isotropic and uniform, which overlooks the extension-twist interaction and the presence of lumen.

The elastic behaviour of an individual fibre embedded in a fibre mat is modelled based on the assumptions and approximations outlined by Schulgasser and Page [6], although the fibre is not modelled as an angle-ply laminate, but as a transversely isotropic material since the fibril angle is known to vary considerably in wood pulp fibres. The in-plane elastic behaviour of a fibre is described by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{LL} \\ \sigma_{TT} \\ \tau_{LT} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & Q_{16} \\ Q_{21} & Q_{22} & Q_{26} \\ Q_{61} & Q_{62} & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{LL} \\ \varepsilon_{TT} \\ \gamma_{LT} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where stiffness components are related to engineering elastic constants by $Q_{11} = E_L/(1 - \nu_{LT}\nu_{TL})$, $Q_{22} = E_T/(1 - \nu_{LT}\nu_{TL})$, $Q_{12} = \nu_{LT}E_T/(1 - \nu_{LT}\nu_{TL})$, $Q_{66} = G_{LT}$, and $Q_{16} = Q_{61} = Q_{26} = Q_{62} = 0$. The longitudinal Young's modulus and transverse Young's modulus of the fibres are denoted E_L and E_T , respectively, and the major and minor Poisson ratio ν_{LT} and ν_{TL} , respectively. However to account for the inherent porosity of the fibres and the fibre mat the stiffness matrix of the fibre should be multiplied with the ratio of the density of the fibre mat ρ and density of the fibre wall ρ_f , which can

simply be interpreted the volume fraction of the fibres in the fibre mat. The density of the fibre mat is defined as the ratio of its grammage and thickness and the density of the fibre wall can be assumed to be 1500 kg/m³ [13]. The effective stiffness matrix for fibre mat layer with a non-uniform fibre orientation distribution $p(\theta)$ can be obtained through a laminate analogy (e.g. [14]).

$$[\bar{Q}]_i = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\frac{\pi}{2}}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} [T(\theta)]^{-1} [Q] [T(\theta)] p(\theta) d\theta \quad (9)$$

Based on the work of Hashin [15] on the effective thermal expansion coefficients of polycrystalline materials in terms of the anisotropic thermoelastic properties of the constituting crystals, Schulgasser [5] obtained an exact relationship between hygro- (or thermal-) expansion coefficients and elastic compliances of polycrystalline aggregates. The result is valid for hexagonal, tetragonal and trigonal constituting crystals and applicable to any composite material composed of a single type of constituent of the required elastic symmetries. For a composite with the effective compliance tensor \bar{S}_{ijkl} and the constituent compliance tensor S_{ijkl}^c , the hygroexpansion coefficients of the constituent material β_1 and β_2 are related to the effective hygroexpansion tensor of the composite by [5]

$$\bar{\beta}_{ij} = \frac{(\bar{S}_{11ij} + \bar{S}_{22ij})(\beta_1 - \beta_2) + (S_1\beta_2 - S_1\beta_2)\delta_{ij}}{S_1 - S_2} \quad (10)$$

where δ_{ij} is Kronecker's delta function and

$$S_1 = S_{1111}^c + S_{1122}^c \quad (11)$$

$$S_2 = S_{1122}^c + S_{2222}^c \quad (12)$$

It was shown in [16] that although the Eq. (10) is not strictly valid for porous materials, it still describes the hygrothermal behaviour adequately of such materials. The assumption of transverse isotropy of the fibres in this study (hexagonal symmetry) allows for determination of the macroscopic hygroexpansion behaviour of the fibre mat provided that the elastic and hygroexpansion behaviour of the constituent fibres as well as the macroscopic elastic behaviour of the fibre mat are known. Considering the special nature of the constituting fibre material that have a very small hygrothermal expansion in the fibril direction and relatively large expansion in perpendicular direction [17], the most important property resulting in hygroscopic dimensional changes is the coefficient of moisture expansion of the fibre in the transverse direction. Reconsidering Eq. (10) and postulating the same assumptions as in [16], and neglecting the hygroexpansion in the fibre direction compared with the transverse direction, the effective coefficients of hygroexpansion for a fibre mat layer can thus be calculated as

$$\{\bar{\beta}\}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{S}_{11} + \bar{S}_{12} \\ \bar{S}_{12} + \bar{S}_{22} \\ \frac{1}{2}(\bar{S}_{16} + \bar{S}_{26}) \end{bmatrix} \frac{\beta_T}{S_T} \quad (13)$$

where \bar{S}_{11} , \bar{S}_{12} , \bar{S}_{22} , \bar{S}_{16} and \bar{S}_{26} are the components of the effective compliance matrix given by the inverse of the stiffness matrix in Eq. (9) and S_T is defined as the strain in the transverse direction due to unit isotropic stress applied to a single fibre, i.e. the sum of the components the fibre compliance matrix in the transverse direction.

The immediate implication of this approach is that the macroscopic hygroexpansion and elastic properties of the fibre mat are sufficient to determine the coefficient of hygroexpansion of the

fibres. The coefficient of hygroexpansion of the fibres in the transverse direction can be obtained by linking the micromechanical relationship for the effective hygroexpansion in Eq. (13) and the effective stiffness matrix in Eq. (9) of every fibre mat layer to the macroscopic curl measurements of the fibre mat in Eq. (5):

$$\beta_T = \frac{(\{\Delta M^*\} - [A^*]\{\Delta N^*\})^T [B^*]\{\Delta \kappa\}}{|\{\Delta M^*\} - [A^*]\{\Delta N^*\}|^2} \quad (14)$$

where

$$\{\Delta N^*\} = \frac{\Delta C \langle t \rangle}{S_T} \sum_{i=1}^n [\bar{Q}]_i \begin{bmatrix} \bar{S}_{11} + \bar{S}_{12} \\ \bar{S}_{12} + \bar{S}_{22} \\ \frac{1}{2}(\bar{S}_{16} + \bar{S}_{26}) \end{bmatrix}_i (z_i - z_{i-1}) \quad (15)$$

$$\{\Delta M^*\} = \frac{\Delta C \langle t^2 \rangle}{2S_T} \sum_{i=1}^n [\bar{Q}]_i \begin{bmatrix} \bar{S}_{11} + \bar{S}_{12} \\ \bar{S}_{12} + \bar{S}_{22} \\ \frac{1}{2}(\bar{S}_{16} + \bar{S}_{26}) \end{bmatrix}_i (z_i^2 - z_{i-1}^2) \quad (16)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fibre orientation distribution through the thickness of the fibre mat

The in plane fibre orientation distribution of a fibre mat layer (no. 77) that is shown in Fig. 3 reveal that fibres are predominantly oriented in the MD as could be expected from the processing conditions of the fibre mat. The wireside layer of the fibre mat contains more fibres aligned in the MD than the topside layer. The degree of orientation is diminishing from the wire to the topside of sheet with a linearly decreasing concentration parameter of the von Mises distribution function of the fibre orientation. It can be concluded that fibre orientation distribution of fibre mats manufactured with the dynamic sheet former has a thickness gradient, which shows evidence of a significant two-sidedness. The result is in accordance with Lloyd and Chalmers [9] who determined the fibre orientation distribution for paper samples formed in a dynamic sheet former from mechanical pulp. Furthermore, it was found that fibre mats manufactured with the dynamic sheet former in this study have a fibre orientation distribution that is symmetric with respect to the MD throughout the thickness of the sheet.

Fig. 3 (a) Scanned image of the wireside fibre layer, and (b) a local high-resolution magnification, with (c) the corresponding fibre orientation distribution.

The arrangement of fibres in the thickness direction of the fibre mat changes from being more layered at the wireside of the fibre mat to being more felted at the topside of the fibre mat. In the beginning of the formation the fibres will settle on the wire and orient in the direction of the rotation. As the formation of the sheet progresses the fibres will settle on a fibre network which leads to fibre entanglement and a z-directional orientation. The z-directional orientation of the fibres due to increasing surface unevenness with increasing sheet thickness, and migration of mobile fibres to inner structure from the topside of the sheet due to dewatering pressure created by the centrifugal force during drainage.

For certain applications where the composite panels need to remain flat, it is crucial to use a material that does not curl if the relative humidity in the environment is changed. With laminate mechanics it is possible to quantitatively address this problem. The laminate structure can be designed to suppress or even eliminate dimensional instability by out-of-plane buckling. One way to suppress dimensional instability is to assure a symmetric lay-up, i.e. hygroexpansion would only occur in the plane and in the thickness direction, and not result in any curvature. This could be achieved by using an even number of fibre mats in the composite, and by stacking them symmetrically. Another way would be to assure that the hygroexpansion is equal in each layer, although this would be difficult to control for a general laminate since the hygroexpansion is intimately linked with the stiffness properties in each layer. Out-of-plane buckling could be suppressed by maximizing the $[\bar{D}]$ matrix, i.e. the bending stiffness. A sandwich type of laminate, with stiffer layers on the top and bottom should prevent excessive curvature. To prevent or stem the ingress of moisture by using a barrier layer on the outside of the composite is naturally also an option. Finally, the simplest way would be to avoid hygroexpansion altogether by using fibres that do not swell. Cellulose fibres that have been hornified are known to swell and shrink to a considerably smaller extent [18, 19]. In summary, the proposed models can also be used quantitatively to address microstructural design of the composite material to avoid or restrain dimensional instability.

The transverse coefficient of moisture expansion of the wood fibres

Because of the intrinsic hygroscopic properties of the fibres and the fibre orientation distribution thickness gradient, dimensional changes will be larger in the CD than in the MD of a fibre mat. Since the in-plane deformation will vary in the thickness direction, the curl in the CD (around the MD axis) will be more pronounced than curl in the MD. Due to the fibre orientation distribution symmetry with respect to the MD throughout its thickness, the fibre mat is not prone to twisting.

The dominating curl component is in the CD (Fig. 4). The curvature was determined by analysing 10 different images of each specimen. Coordinates were taken along the upper edge of the strip to quantify the deflected shape of the specimen. The radius of curvature was evaluated from the circle with the best least squares fit to the coordinate data. The curvature was then calculated as the inverse of the radius.

Fig. 4 Measured curvature for three specimens at (a) 0% RH and (b) 50% RH. The specimens are curled around the MD axis pointing out of the paper.

The thickness measurements showed in a thickness increase from 0.565 mm to 0.583 mm, about 3%, over the humidity range. The density of the fibre mat evaluated at 50% RH is 327.5 kg/m³.

The experimental results were used as input to the laminate model to calculate the coefficient of hygroexpansion of the unbleached softwood kraft pulp fibres used in this study. The

Young's modulus of the fibre in the longitudinal direction E_L is 33 GPa [14]. Based on values found in the literature by Nordin [20] it is assumed that the transverse Young's modulus E_T is half that of the longitudinal Young's modulus E_L , the shear modulus G_{LT} amounts to a third of E_L , and the major Poisson ratio is 0.3. The effective elastic properties of every layer can be assessed with Eq. (9) which can readily be discretized into a sum since the fibre orientation distribution $p(\theta)$ was quantified for discrete intervals (see Fig. 3). The tensile-shear interaction effects in the laminate as a whole were very small since the fibre orientation distribution is symmetric with respect to the MD throughout the thickness of the sheet. This interaction could therefore be neglected. Using the experimental results from all specimens, i.e. the difference in curvature when the specimens were subjected to a change in moisture content from 0 % and 7.6 % (taken from the sorption isotherm plot in Fig. 5) the coefficient of hygroexpansion is calculated with Eq. (14) to 0.11 percent strain per percent change in moisture content. The results are summarised in Tab. 1.

EXPERIMENTAL				CALCULATED
Relative humidity RH [%]	Moisture content C [%]	Thickness t [mm]	Curvature κ_{CD} [m ⁻¹]	Coefficient of hygroexpansion β_T [%/% ΔC]
0	0	0.565 (0.002)	1.990 (0.478)	0.112 (0.039)
50	7.6	0.583 (0.007)	0.954 (0.36)	

Tab.1 Results summary. Average values (standard deviations).

Fig. 5 Equilibrium sorption isotherm at 30 °C in adsorption for the fibre mat.

The value of the coefficient of hygroexpansion obtained in this study for unbleached softwood kraft fibres, $\beta_T = 0.112$, can be compared to values for similar cellulosic fibres found in literature. Typical values of hygroexpansion coefficients of wood fibres in the transverse direction vary from 0.17-0.22 [21] but values up to 0.6 [17] can be found. However, the latter value is based on the assumption of saturation moisture content of 35 % and zero fibril angle of the cellulosic fibres that expand approximately 20 % in the transverse direction over the range of relative humidity from 0 % to 100 % at room temperature. The values obtained with the model presented in this study are not far from the values reported in the literature determined from single wood fibres by means of costly and cumbersome experiments on individual fibres with a large scatter. Consequently, the model and method developed here can be used for screening suitable types of wood fibres with regard to hygroexpansive behaviour in materials selection before manufacturing the composite material.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been showed that the fibre orientation distribution varies through the thickness in fibre mats manufactured by dynamic sheet formation. This variability gives rise to a change in curvature if the ambient relative humidity is changed. Measurements of the curvature change can be used constructively to estimate the hygroexpansion coefficient of the fibre. Necessary input data in the laminate mechanics model is the fibre orientation distribution through the thickness, the fibre mat grammage, the elastic properties of the fibre, and thickness and curvature measurements. Experiments on a conifer kraft pulp fibre mat gave a moisture expansion coefficient of 0.11, which is comparable to literature values. The proposed methodology may be used to quantitatively assess the potential of different wood fibres as composite reinforcement where dimensional stability is of importance.

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